

EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES AT THE CLUJ MEDICAL UNIVERSITY DURING GLOBAL HEALTHCARE CRISIS

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Abstract

Purpose – We present aspects regarding the managerial and organizational challenges in order to ensure the highest possible educational results inside the Medical University of Cluj-Napoca during the most severe global medical crisis of our times, the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Methodology/approach – In order to challenge our thesis, we designed and conducted several questionnaires for all the parties involved in the educational process. Both students and teaching professors were asked to fulfill the questionnaires.

Findings – Our results refer to the challenges and organizational efforts of transferring a well-established and acknowledge educational system in a very short time exclusive in the online dimension. We present valuable information for each significant section from the educational process of medical specialists.

Research limitations/implications – We only conducted this study inside the Medical University of Cluj-Napoca. As one the most important educational institution in this field, the results of our study may apply to other educational institutions, as all the educational system in Romania was heavily impacted during the 2020 spring lock-down.

Practical implications – The results of these study might be of great interest for all the parties acting in the educational system, mostly for medical branches, but not only. Especially those involved in the design of the educational system can find valuable data for the future, as being prepared for future possible lockdowns.

Originality/value – The study implies parties directly involved in the educational system during the spring lock-down of 2020. The structure and design of our surveys were both adapted to the needs and target sphere of respondents.

Key words: Global Medical Crisis, Educational Management Challenges, Healthcare System.

Introduction

COVID-19 Pandemic, the world's largest healthcare crisis changed everybody's lifestyle, the humanity faces challenges and restrictions in social distancing like never before. What started as a local healthcare crisis, became very fast a global crisis with impact in almost all the aspects of social reality. First healthcare systems were affected, then education, economics, financial, government measures, social habits suffer major challenges.

Governments are taking actions imposing restrictions in order to keep the pandemic under control are heavy disputed, as control of pandemic also implies control of population, in some opinions, even beyond the limits of human rights.

For the teaching professors in the medical universities, this crisis brought two dimensions: They had to concentrate on both medical activity as doctors, but also on the teaching activity inside the university. They had to adapt with highspeed on both dimensions.

As the COVID-19 threat is far from being overrun and second or third wave appear in different countries on the globe, it is hard for specialists and governments to predict social distancing measures for mid-term. All the statements and decisions are taken mostly according to the very oscillating evolution of the pandemic in the region.

With major impact on the educational systems, further possible physical restrictions will have to be overrun by creative solution supported by technology and digitalization. What will be the future in education of medical staff? What challenges are we facing while completely renouncing at educational methods that require in person presence? What opportunities appear while all educational systems apply major changes and many resources are allocated to the educational systems world-wide?

Hypotheses

The educational systems were under high pressure as social distancing during lock downs which blocked most of the traditional education forms, was imposed suddenly. As COVID-19 provoked a global crisis, governments had to act specific to the crisis management decision style. Crisis management also implies fast decisions which most of the times upset the affected environment because of the lack of adaption periods. Therefore, our hypotheses are that the high pressure on the medical educational system obliged the system to adapt with very high speed. The high access level to technology and communication systems made the conversion to online education easy in the field of theoretical education. The challenges in the practical part of the educational process are still very high, some aspects remain still unsolved. Solutions in this part of practical education without in person contact are still expected.

While the medical educational system was the most affected educational system, not only because the most of the teaching staff was also in the first line of fighting this global medical crisis, but also the students could not interfere with the core of their studies: the patients. Unlike other fields of activity, the medicine students suffered the most, because the patients they had to come in contact with, during the practical stages were representing a great risk of spreading the virus. In fact, on a world-wide scale, many hospitals became source of spreading the virus, not because lack of risk management measures, but simply because the general medical healthcare system was overrun and was not prepared for such a big scale of this pandemic.

As every major change brings risks and opportunities, we are looking at both of them in order to decrease the lacks and risk of poor qualitative education and also increase the advantage brought by new opportunities in the field of education. We studied this perspective during all the stages of the educational process for medical staff.

Methodology

Our interdisciplinary team which covers specialists in medicine, teaching, research and management designed two different questionnaires, one for students and one for professors. Although both instruments have the same structure, specific topics are analyzed from different perspectives and the questions are adapted to the targeted responders.

Our instruments follow a strict structure which follows the main stages of the educational process at the University of Medicine Iuliu Hatieganu from Cluj-Napoca. In this order we first looked at the available infrastructure by taking into consideration only the new aspects imposed the social distancing and the 2020 spring-lock-down. For now, we find no need to focus on deep topics like content development, as this kind of changes require much more time than few months, but this might become a topic of further studies, depending on the evolution of the educational systems. This section is also very relevant for the adaptation process to the new teaching environment, almost exclusive online.

The second part of our instruments refer to the theoretical teaching system. By comparing both traditional and crisis – online teaching system we are also interested of new findings regarding the field of teaching techniques for improvement of theoretical knowledge transfer.

The third and maybe the most critical part of our study takes into consideration the practical part, which was heavy impacted by the lock-down and social distancing measures. As presented before, medical professionals have to prepare themselves for interaction with patients. In these first stages of the global healthcare crisis, the medical educational system was not prepared to accomplish the need of interaction

between students and patients because of the very high risk of contamination. For sure, on the long run, the educational system will have to improve in order to fulfill the needs on active interaction between students and patients.

Another important stage of our instrument reflects appreciations regarding the examination system. As one of the most effective quality guaranties of the educational system, the examination of acquired knowledge, was also questioned in order to check if it reflects the needs and if it allows enough adaptation freedom in respect to each course versus standardization.

The last part of our study is reserved to present unique techniques and general improvement points of the new online teaching system and also to help extract and present the most important conclusions of this study.

Results

The first part of our study focuses on the access to required technology in order to continue the interactive educational process during social and physical distancing measures.

Regarding the access to internet, the professors seem to be very satisfied, 71% of them consider having had excellent access to internet connection. With few exceptions the majority of over 93% of both of professors and students had satisfying or excellent access internet connection. In fact, good access to internet connection made it possible to continue the studies in online medium during the spring-lock-down. Figure 1. presents the above-mentioned results.

Figure 1. Access to internet connection

While over 93% of professors and students claim to not have any problems with access to the necessary devices, the results presented in figure 2. shows that most of our responders prefer laptop and smartphone. While tablets seem to have a very low usability, the usage of desktops seems to be rather preferred by professors. An explanation to this is the higher possibility that professors own an office at home, while students still have to rely on portability.

Figure 2. Access to devices

Overall, the adaptation challenges to the online environment for both professors and students seems to be overrun with no particular major inconvenience. In fact, 35% of professors and 32% of students say they had no problem at all and 28% and 32% of professor's respective students say it was hard to adapt but they found useful support. Other aspects reveal that the younger generation, the students adapt faster and easier to changes.

Figure 3. Adaptation challenges

Another interesting aspect is that 55% of the students say that they left the university city during the semester. This was possible due to the online classes. From the logistic point of view, students don't lose time to get/come back from university, another advantage mentioned in the responses of the students.

The second part of our study presents the challenges faced at the theoretical classes. In the beginning of this part, we should mention that 29% of the students consider online classes more efficient than traditional classrooms, while 41% think the opposite. 29% consider the efficiency of both ways as equal. If we take into consideration that only 41% prefer the traditional classroom after only one semester, the chances that online education will take proportion is very high.

A comparison between professor's vs student's choice between classroom vs online education regarding the theoretical aspects reveals that professors are rather more resistant to change, only 7% of them would prefer online classes, compared with 20% of students. Very important is the fact that a large number of responders do not consider the environment as important but rather the teaching techniques. A percentage of 42% of professors and 38% of students think likewise.

Figure 4. Online vs classroom theoretical lessons

Another comparison is the subjective evaluation of meeting the actual requirements. Related to this, students seem to be more exigent than professors. Figure 5. presents the answers, where both professors and students have evaluated from a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means that the online training does not meet the actual requirements and 5 means that the requirements are fully fulfilled.

Figure 5. Theoretical education meets requirements

With the next topic, we seem to reach a sensitive topic: the capacity to remain focused during online trainings or the capacity to maintain the audience attention in online trainings. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents a very poor capacity to maintain attention and 5 represents a very high capacity to maintain the attention, the professor's answers are more concentrated around a neutral evaluation, meaning that they had not really a challenge regarding focusing during the classes. On the other hand, the students admit that 36% of them have major challenges on remaining focused during online classes.

Figure 6. Capacity to remain focused

Furthermore, different pedagogical techniques like quiz, role-play, scenario, etc. were inserted in the online trainings. While the professor's opinion regarding the efficiency of these exercises is equally divided in two, the students do not appreciate this. 78.8 percent of the students do not consider that these exercises bring added value in comparison with the direct interaction with the professor and patient.

The third part of our study presents aspects on the practical training of the students. The results reveal critical aspects regarding the practical training of medicine students. 12% of the students and 21% of professors think the stages should be taught again, as the incapacity of getting in direct contact with the patients has a major impact on the educational process. Another 72% of the students and 50% of professors admit that practical stages are highly impacted when delivered in online and only 3 percent of students think that the educational act is not impacted.

On another question regarding the lack of time spent in hospital with patients reveals the same problem. 42% of professors and 60% of students admit this will have a major impact and 12% of students and 28% of professors think that this impacts the education severely, so the practical stages in hospital need to be recovered in the following semesters. Both professors and students admit in 71% and 54% that students have to invest more time in their theoretical preparation because the lack of practical stages in hospitals. They are also convinced, 92% and 97% of professors and students, that the online activity cannot replace the practical stages in hospitals.

The fourth part of our study presents aspects regarding challenges in the evaluation process of the acquired information. As presumed, the two categories of professors and students have very different opinions regarding the evaluation process. 81% of the students do not see a problem if the examination process is readapted while 53% and 46% of professor see a major impact respectively a small impact on the future generation of medics. This year, the exams were concentrated in 10 minutes per student per discipline. This had a certain impact on the stress level on students. The impact is presented in Figure 7. It seems that students, as they were the ones examined in this case, feel a higher level of stress than the professors would expect.

We also present improvement points gathered both from professors and students like: the implementation of a dedicated online platform or app better suited for examination. There should be more time (more than 10 minutes) for the examination. Development of virtual patients for the long run. Another improvement could be the possibility for students to choose the date of the exam from at least 2 options. Focus on what students learned. Evaluation can be an ongoing process during the classes. Intermediate presentations, essay or papers could represent a large amount of the final mark.

Figure 7. Impact on stress during online exams

Discussion and Conclusions

The general opinion of students is that theoretical courses can be taught remotely, while practical works are impossible to be taught online. Therefore, it's hard to consider that a permanent online teaching method is a long-term solution. Probably not even a medium term one. Also, the evaluation method is problematic, since it is dependent on a lot of technical parameters that can bring bad results even if the student is a hard learning one. As a positive feedback, online courses can have its advantages, since they can be watched later and remain store for later consultancy. In the online courses there can be integrated images and videos that help the student to understand the topics. On the other hand, a long course, held online brings no interaction and attention is lost easily.

The professor's point of view is that online courses should be a complementary measure, for completing the educational activity, not the replacement for it. If there is the case, universities should help the professors to build the need infrastructure and adapt to the tooling. The online exams have a positive result, since the system corrects automatically the exams and information is easily kept into the archive.

Notes

Our study presents the main challenges in the educational process at Iuliu Hatieganu University of Medicine and Pharmacy Cluj-Napoca during the first so called online semester in the history of the University. Due to the lock-down forced by the COVID-19 greatest global crisis in regarding social distancing, neither educational system nor students and professors were prepared for such a fast reaction. In our opinion, because all the universities were able to continue the educational process in such hard conditions is an accomplishment that had to be mentioned and highly appreciated. Because of great adaptation speed many challenges were overrun, nor necessary all of them in the best form. Our goal was to present the challenges and effects, as well as possible improvement points for the future.

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